

ARTICLE: THE EFFECT OF GUIDED DISCOVERY LEARNING MODELS ON MATHEMATICAL FLOWING VIEWED FROM THE INITIAL CAPABILITY OF MATHEMATICS

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Abstract: This study aims to obtain empirical data about differences in students mathematical reasoning that are taught with the learning model used, namely guided discovery learning models and direct learning models reviewed from students' initial mathematical abilities. Quasi-experimental research with design 2×2 treatment by level was carried out in class X SMK Negeri 1 Boalemo even semester 2014-2015 Academic Year. Research data was obtained through mathematical reasoning tests and preliminary math ability tests. Analysis of mathematical reasoning data which is grouped based on the initial math ability test scores which become attribute variables includes high and low initial abilities. Research data is analyzed in two parts, namely analysis of description and inferential analysis to test the research statistical hypothesis. This research produces findings, namely: (1) There are differences in students' mathematical reasoning between students who are learned by guided discovery learning models with direct learning models. (2) There is an interaction between the guided discovery learning model and the initial ability to mathematical reasoning abilities. (3) Mathematical reasoning of students who are taught by discovery discovery learning models is higher than direct learning models for students with high initial abilities. (4) Mathematical reasoning of students who are taught with guided discovery learning models is lower than the direct learning model for students with low initial abilities.

Keywords: Guided Discovery Learning Model, Direct Learning Model, Mathematical Reasoning and Early Mathematical Ability.

INTRODUCTION

National education system (in Law 2003: 20) states that education is a conscious and planned effort to realize a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character and skills needed by him, society, nation and country.

One important part in the field of education is mathematics. As stated in Permen No. 22 of 2006, which states that mathematics is a universal science that underlies the development of modern technology.

In Education Unit Level Curriculum for mathematics subjects stated that the general purpose of mathematics education is emphasized on students to have the following aspects: (1) Understand and explain the interrelationship between concepts and apply them in problem solving, (2) Using mathematical reasoning, (3) Solve mathematical problems, (4) Communicate mathematical ideas, (5) Appreciate the usefulness of mathematics in life, (6) Develop the ability to reason logically, critically and creatively (Depdiknas, 2006: 429).

Likewise, the goals expected in learning mathematics by the *National Council of Teachers of Mathematics* (NCTM). NCTM (2000) defined five standard mathematical ability to be possessed by the students, the ability of problem solving (*problemsolving*), communication skills (*communication*), the ability of the connection (*connection*), reasoning (*reasoning*), and the ability of representation (*representation*), (in Sroyer Agustina, 2013: 25).

As a subject, mathematics can equip students with the ability to think logically, analytically, systematically, critically and creatively as well as the ability to cooperate. This competence is needed so that students can have the ability to acquire, manage, and utilize information to survive in an ever-changing and uncertain situation. One of the competencies in question is students' reasoning abilities. The ability to reason makes students able to solve problems in their lives, inside and outside of school. Whenever someone uses reasoning to validate his thinking, it can increase an individual's confidence with mathematics and think mathematically.

The above is the hope dreamed of learning outcomes in the process of learning mathematics. However, this is not in accordance with the existing reality, one of the facts that shows that the learning outcomes of mathematics in Indonesia are still far from expectations. According to Balitbang-Depdiknas (in Santoso, 2013) the level of ability in mastering mathematics in Indonesian students is still low, this can be seen from the results of the 2012 PISA (test *Program for International Student Assessment*) dividing student achievement in six skill levels, from level 1 (lowest) to level 6 (highest) for mathematics and science.

Another problem is that mathematics learning still tends to focus on textbooks, teachers generally in teaching use a lot of lecture and expository methods in learning. This was agreed by Ruseffendi (2006: 54) who stated that during this time in the process of learning mathematics in class, students generally learned mathematics only told by the teacher and not through exploration activities. This fact shows that students are not active in learning. Through this learning process, it is unlikely that mathematical reasoning abilities, especially students' mathematical reasoning, can develop and students tend to be difficult in mathematical reasoning.

One alternative is a guided discovery learning model. Wicolx (in Suprihatiningrum, 2013: 241-242) says that in guided discovery learning, students are encouraged to learn actively through their own active involvement with concepts, principles, and teachers to encourage students to have experience and conduct experiments that allow students find principles for themselves.

In addition to learning approaches or models, other factors that influence the success of a learning process are students themselves. Students have characteristics that can influence student learning activities, including: background of knowledge, level of knowledge, motivation to learn, learning style, level of maturity, initial ability, socio-economic environment, intelligence, and others.

From this description, the writer will conduct research formulated in the title of the study: the ***influence of discovery learning models guided on mathematical reasoning in terms of the students' initial abilities.***

Reasoning in the dictionary of Indonesian language is defined as "how (prihal) to use reason; thought or way of logical thinking. Whereas according to the English dictionary reasoning mentioned "*reasoning*". Fadjar Shadiq (2004: 2) defines that reasoning is an activity, a process or an activity of thinking to draw conclusions or make a correct new statement based on several statements whose truth has been proven or assumed beforehand. Ministry of National Education (2004: 6) states that "Mathematical material and mathematical reasoning are two things that cannot be separated, namely mathematical material understood through mathematical reasoning and mathematical reasoning is understood through learning mathematics. The term mathematical reasoning in some literature is called *mathematical reasoning*. According to Karin Brodie (in Suyantana, 2011: 11) states that: "*Mathematical reasoning is reasoning about and with the object of mathematics.*" From the above statement it can be interpreted that mathematical reasoning is reasoning about mathematical objects.

Based on the above description, mathematical reasoning can be synthesized is the ability to think someone to learn how to make decisions logically and provide arguments based on mathematical information and understand it.

Dirjen Dikdasmen Regulation Number 506 / C / Kep / PP / 2004 dated November 11, 2004 concerning report cards as quoted by (Sri Wardhani, 2010: 14) reasoning ability is able to: (1) put forward allegations; (2) doing mathematical manipulation; (3) draw conclusions, compile evidence, provide reasons or proof of the truth of the solution; (4) draw conclusions from the statement; (5) checking the validity of an argument; (6) determine the pattern or nature of mathematical symptoms to make generalizations.

Indicators of mathematical reasoning abilities developed in this study include: (1) doing mathematical manipulation; (2) compile evidence, provide reasons for several solutions; (3) draw conclusions; (4) giving an explanation of the model, picture, fact, nature, relationship, pattern, or problem that exists.

According to Chaplin (Petra, 1997: 34) abilities are skills, agility, talent and ability as an energy to do an action. The ability that has been attached to a person and related to new things that will be studied is then called the initial ability, (Pentatito, 2008: 28). Meanwhile, according to Dick and Carry (in Anis, 2011: 30) states that the initial ability (*entery behavior*) is defined as the knowledge and skills that students must possess as long as they continue to the next level. If viewed from the level of mastery, the initial ability can be classified into 3 types, namely: initial ability to be ready to use, initial ability to be ready again and initial ability to recognize (Uno, 2008: 161). According to Muchlishin (2010: 8-9) the initial ability of mathematics is a capability possessed by students both natural and learned to carry out certain actions historically where they give a positive or negative response to the object using reasoning and ways of thinking logical, analytical, systematic, critical, creative and innovative and emphasizes the mastery of concepts and algorithms in addition to problem solving abilities.

From this description, the initial ability of mathematics is the initial ability that students have which is a prerequisite for learning further lessons that are inherent in students in the form of ready-to-use abilities, readiness ability as well as recognition skills acquired by students through mathematics learning activities. Statistics prerequisite materials are basic mathematical abilities. With indicators students have a memory of mathematics lessons that have been learned before (addition of numbers, reduction of numbers, multiplication of numbers, division of numbers, and reading data in the form of diagrams).

Markaban (2008: 11) reveals a guided discovery learning model is a learning model that involves a dialogue / interaction between students and teachers where students look for the desired conclusion through a sequence of questions conducted by the teacher. According to Eggen and Don Kauchak (2012: 177), the guided finding model is a teaching approach in which the teacher gives students examples of specific topics and guides students to understand the topic.

From the definition of experts, it can be synthesized that the guided discovery learning model is a way or process of learning that involves students and teachers starting with the way the teacher gives questions and examples to students, the teacher guides students to understand concepts, and students find their own answers to a problem.

Carin (1993) in (Suprihatiningrum, 2013: 246-247), gives instructions in planning guided discovery learning, including: 1) determining learning objectives; 2) choosing a model / method that is in accordance with the discovery activities; 3) making data observation sheets for students; 4) prepare complete equipment and materials; 5) determine carefully whether students will work individually or in groups of 2-5 students; 6) try first the activities that will be done by students to find out the difficulties that might arise or the possibility for modification.

One of the learning media that can be used is to use LKS (student worksheets). Questions can be given when learning takes place as an exercise, homework assignments or at the end of the test learning a subject.

According to Arends (2008: 295) the direct learning model is a teacher-centered model, which consists of five steps in its implementation, namely: *set up*, explanation or demonstration, *guided practice*, feedback and *extended practice*. Direct learning model is a teacher-centered model and based on three characteristics: 1) the type of student produced; 2) the flow or syntax in the learning process; 3) the learning environment, (Suprihatiningrum, 2013: 229).

Paul Eggen and Don Kauchak (2013: 368) phases in applying lessons with direct learning models consisting of 4 (four) phases, namely: phase 1) introduction and review; phase 2) presentation; phase 3) guided training; phase 4) self-training.

Based on the various opinions above, the direct learning model can be synthesized a learning process or process that emphasizes mastery of concepts or behavioral change by prioritizing the deductive approach by identifying learning objectives, material structure, and basic skills that will be taught to achieve learning goals, as well as a teacher-centered learning. Phase or stages in direct learning are: (1) conveying learning objectives; (2) convey knowledge to students, provide modeling or demonstration, (3) guide and train students; (4) provide opportunities for students to practice applying concepts or skills that have been learned, and (5) provide feedback.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Place and Time Research: This research was carried out at SMK Negeri 1 Boalemo. SMK Negeri 1 Boalemo has 24 study groups consisting of 8 classes of 8 classes with a total of 217 students, class XI as many as 8 classes with a total of 182 students, class XII as many as 8 classes with a total of 194 students. This research was conducted in the even semester of 2014-2015 Academic Year, which included the implementation of learning activities with the discovery learning model guided and direct learning models, mathematical reasoning tests, data processing, to the preparation of research reports.

Type and Design of Research: This type of research is a quasi-experimental research that is giving treatment in the form of a guided discovery learning model and the application of a direct learning model in mathematics learning. The experimental design that will be used in this research is the experiment *treatment by level*. While the design of the analysis of this study is a 2factorial design 2×2 . The sorting factor is the moderator variable of students' initial mathematical abilities. Sorting is divided into two levels: high initial mathematical ability above the group average (33% from above) and low initial math ability below the group average (33% from below) after the data is sorted from the largest to the smallest .

Population and Research Sample: The population in this study were students of vocational schools in Boalemo Regency. Therefore the target *population* of this study is students of State Vocational High School 1 Boalemo, while the affordable *population* is the tenth grade students of State Vocational High School 1 Boalemo. The technique of determining the sample in this research was carried out by means of *multi-stage random, random* sampling namely the sampling of members of the population without regard to the existing strata. From the Multi stage random sampling, 2 classes were selected, namely class X TKJ A and X TKJ B as the experimental class and 2 other selected classes namely class X TIPTL and class X Accounting as the control class.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Discussion of Research Results

The hypothesis **first** proposed in this study is "there are differences in students' mathematical reasoning that are taught with guided discovery learning models and direct learning models". Overall the application of the discovery learning model is guided by students' mathematical reasoning higher than the direct learning model. The superiority of guided discovery models in mathematics learning, can not be separated from the substance, namely a learning process that challenges students to solve a problem that has been designed so that students get important knowledge by processing the information that already exists and compile their knowledge about solving existing problems. Problems designed in the guided discovery model are real problems related to everyday life, so that students feel curious and take the initiative to know and understand the meaning of the subject matter. This learning model also requires students to work together and participate in teams to develop independence and self-confidence, because at the end of the objectives of this learning model students will develop their knowledge, develop *discovery* and higher level thinking skills.

From the description above it can be concluded that the application of guided discovery models, both in terms of procedures / stages of learning and from teaching materials used does not reduce the improvement of students' mathematical reasoning. In addition, students feel enthusiastic / respond well to learning procedures that apply guided discovery models.

The results of testing the hypothesis **second** indicate that there is an interaction between the learning model and the initial mathematical ability of students' mathematical reasoning in mathematics subjects. This is because the achievement of learning objectives is influenced by the selection of the right learning model, in addition to the students' initial mathematical ability to the material being studied also influences. Students with high mathematics initial abilities who are taught with guided discovery learning models achieve higher mathematical reasoning than students who are taught with direct learning models. However, it is inversely proportional to students who have low initial ability, students who are taught by direct learning are higher in mathematical reasoning than students who are taught with guided discovery models. This shows that the effectiveness of a learning model in learning mathematics is related to the initial ability of students. In mathematics learning, students who have low initial math skills are more suitable to be taught by using direct learning models. The form of interaction can be seen in the following figure. Graph of interaction between learning models and students' initial mathematical abilities towards mathematical reasoning.

Figure 1. Interaction between learning models and students' initial ability to mathematical reasoning.

Figure 1. Shows a considerable difference between the mathematical reasoning of students who have high mathematics initial abilities who are taught with direct learning (= 60.78) and those who are taught with guided discovery models (= 79.39).

Hypothesis **Third**: for students who have the initial ability of high mathematics mathematics learning outcomes students who follow guided discovery learning models are higher than the direct learning model.

From the results of data analysis and research findings, it has been tested that there are differences in mathematical reasoning of students who have high mathematics initial abilities that are taught by guided discovery learning models and direct learning. Furthermore, the mathematical reasoning of students who have high mathematics initial abilities taught by guided discovery models have an average score of 79.39 higher than students' mathematical reasoning with direct learning with an average score of 60.78. This was also indicated by the Tukey (Q) test of 8.65 which was significant. Learning with guided discovery models is very appropriate compared to direct learning to be applied to students with high mathematics abilities.

In the guided discovery learning model, the action of students in learning starts from the existence of problems that will be solved and stated in questions or statements. where students will apply their knowledge or try to find out the knowledge needed. Students are active in groups doing learning activities. Learning activities in the guided discovery model by students in the form of an investigation or experiment or find a concept or principle that has been set. Students who have high math skills who have a lot of knowledge about prerequisite material will be very helpful for achieving better mathematical reasoning. In other words, for groups of students who have high initial mathematical abilities, mathematical reasoning that is taught with guided discovery learning models is higher than the direct learning model.

Hepotesis **Fourth**: for students who have low math initial abilities, mathematical reasoning students who follow the direct learning model are higher than the guided discovery learning model.

From the results of data analysis and based on research findings, shows that there are differences in mathematical reasoning of students who have low initial mathematical abilities by following the guided discovery model and direct learning. The results shown by the Tukey (Q) test of 3.93 were significant. From the results of the Tukey test, it shows that students' mathematical reasoning who have a low initial mathematics ability by following learning with a guided discovery model that has an average score () of 60.50 is lower than the direct learning model which has an average score () amounting to 68.94. The results of this study illustrate that learning through direct learning models can improve the mathematical reasoning of students who have low initial mathematical abilities.

Students who have low math skills are identified as having a tendency to be less like to ask questions and less like group work and rather difficult to understand problems. Characteristics of students who have low initial mathematical abilities, have conformity with the characteristics of direct learning implementation. Direct learning model whose main purpose is to help students learn basic skills and knowledge with an emphasis on mastering the material by verbally conveying from the teacher to students. So the activities in direct learning are very supportive of the verbal ability of the brain that has a low initial ability. In the direct learning model students are trained gradually through various exercises to develop their knowledge. The intended knowledge is the ability of students in mathematics including mathematical reasoning. In the structured training stage, students learn or train themselves to complete exercises or tasks as demonstrated or exemplified by the teacher. In the next stage, guided training students are given the opportunity to complete their own training or assignments. In the independent training phase, students are given the opportunity to develop their knowledge in completing exercises or assignments with their language and mathematical

expressions. That is, the implementation of direct learning has not been maximized in balancing the role of teachers and students. Teachers still play a dominant role at each stage of the presentation of learning material.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

CONCLUSION

First, overall, there are differences in mathematics learning outcomes for students who are taught with guided discovery learning models and students who are taught by direct learning models. **Second**, there is an interaction between learning models that are applied to students' initial mathematical abilities towards students' mathematical reasoning. **Third**, for students who have high mathematics initial abilities, mathematical reasoning for students who are taught with guided discovery learning models is higher than students who are taught by direct learning models. **Fourth**, for students who have low initial math skills, students' mathematical reasoning that is taught with discovery learning models is guided lower by students who are taught by direct learning models.

SUGGESTIONS

First, mathematics teachers are advised to use guided discovery learning models and direct learning as a model of alternative organizing in mathematics learning based on student characteristics, especially in the initial ability of students. **Second**, mathematics learning is very loaded with concepts that require high reasoning. In order for mathematical reasoning to be achieved more optimally, the mathematics teachers should always pay attention to the students' initial abilities. So that learning strategies to improve mathematical reasoning can be determined precisely. **Third**, for the perfection of this research, it is suggested to researchers to conduct further research involving other moderator variables, such as self-concept, motivation, thinking style, verbal knowledge, etc., so as to improve students' mathematical reasoning more optimally.

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